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From Code to Cure: Computational Insights into Colon Cancer Biomarker Discovery and Repurposed Drugs

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Colon cancer (CC) is a major global health issue with high incidence and mortality. Despite advances, reliable biomarkers and effective drugs remain limited. This study used integrative bioinformatics and systems biology approaches to identify key genes, regulatory miRNAs, and repurposed drugs related to CC.

Materials and Methods: Gene expression data from the GSE44076 dataset (98 tumor and 98 normal samples) were analyzed to identify DEGs using Limma in R. Feature selection was done with Scikit-learn in Python. A gene co-expression network was built via WGCNA, selecting moderately preserved modules (Zsummary 2–10). mRNA–miRNA networks were constructed using miRWalk, with hub miRNAs identified by Cytoscape. Functional enrichment was performed using DAVID, Reactome, and TAM, and drug–gene interactions were examined with DGIdb.

Results: A total of 6,208 DEGs were identified, and eight key genes—ADH1B, AQP8, CA1, CLCA4, GUCA2B, MMP7, MS4A12, and TMIGD1—were prioritized. Three moderately preserved modules (green-yellow, light cyan, and midnight blue) were selected, containing 203, 453, and 145 genes, respectively. Hub miRNAs such as hsa-let-7b-5p, hsa-miR-6788-5p, and hsa-miR-30c-3p were identified. Key pathways included TGFB, NFkB, and cell cycle signaling. Twenty FDA-approved drugs, including Fluorouracil, Cytarabine, and Tretinoin, showed strong gene interactions.

Conclusion: This computational analysis highlights novel gene–miRNA signatures and drug candidates, warranting further in vitro and in vivo validation for potential application in colon cancer therapy.

Keywords: Colon cancer, Biomarkers, WGCNA, miRNA, Drug repurposing, Bioinformatics, Gene expression analysis

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Introduction

Colon cancer (CC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide, with an estimated 881,000 deaths annually [1]. Despite improvements in screening programs and treatment modalities, the global burden of CC remains significant due to late-stage diagnoses and limited therapeutic precision [2]. Colonoscopy remains the gold standard for diagnosis; however, it is invasive, resource-intensive, and not ideal for large-scale population screening [3].

A major challenge in CC management is the lack of highly specific and sensitive biomarkers for early detection, prognosis, and prediction of treatment response. Conventional treatments such as surgery and chemotherapy often have limited efficacy in advanced disease stages and are associated with significant side effects. Although molecular profiling technologies like microarrays and next-generation sequencing have enabled deeper insights into tumor biology, translating this data into clinically actionable biomarkers and targeted therapies remains a bottleneck [4], [5]. Moreover, emerging evidence indicates that non-coding RNAs (e.g., lncRNAs and miRNAs) play critical roles in colorectal carcinogenesis, yet their integration into clinical practice is still in its infancy [6]. Therefore, there is an urgent need for systems-level approaches that can leverage multi-omics data to uncover novel biomarkers and therapeutic targets in colon cancer.

Many research studies have tried to find useful biomarkers and drugs for CC. Because colon cancer is very common and has a low survival rate, studying it is important [7]. Biomarkers and drugs related to other cancers have also been found in past studies [8]. Compared to traditional lab tests, high-throughput methods can detect more molecules. But they also have problems like differences in sample quality and high noise in data [9]. That is why feature selection is very important in bioinformatics and data science [10]. Feature selection removes noisy and unimportant genes, and keeps those that are most helpful. One simple way is univariate feature selection, which picks the best features using statistical tests. Tools like Scikit-learn in Python provide easy ways to do this [11].

Another useful tool is Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA). This tool builds gene networks and finds modules of related genes [3]. It uses clustering to group genes into modules based on their relationship [12]. Genes that are closely related in biology are put into the same module. WGCNA also uses colors to label these modules. If a gene does not belong to any group, it goes into a "grey" module [13].

In one study about colorectal cancer (CRC), researchers used WGCNA to find modules with low preservation, which means they had big changes in cancer [8]. They found two important miRNAs, hsa-miR-190a-3p and hsa-miR-1277-5p, that might help predict CRC. Also, three bipartite subnetworks were made based on different cancer groups, and possible drugs that could target the selected genes were identified [14], [15].

In another study, WGCNA was used to find CC-related genes from two microarray datasets. They looked for genes with big expression changes. Then, they studied the pathways linked to these genes [16]. This helped researchers understand how these genes might be useful in stopping the cancer from coming back [17]. One more study used WGCNA to understand Alzheimer's disease. They found new miRNAs like miR-615-3p and miR-4722-5p by comparing gene networks from Alzheimer's, mild cognitive impairment, and healthy groups [17], [18].

In this study, the authors used both feature selection and WGCNA methods. First, they built a gene co-expression network using differentially expressed genes (DEGs) [5]. Then, they found modules with low preservation. From these modules, three mRNA-miRNA bipartite networks were created. These networks linked genes to miRNAs that target them. The top miRNAs with the most

connections were chosen for more analysis. Later, the genes that these miRNAs target were checked for possible drug matches [4], [5].

The goal of the research was to discover new miRNAs and potential drugs that can help treat colon cancer [5], [19]. The miRNAs in this study were found to target important genes. These genes were involved in many processes that may affect the development of CC [8], [20]. Finally, some known drugs were also identified that might help treat CC by affecting these target genes [21]. However, these drugs were found only through theoretical and computational methods. Therefore, additional clinical and laboratory investigations are warranted to substantiate their efficacy in real-world therapeutic applications [22].

Material and Methods

- Materials

In this study, we used the dataset from the National Center for Biotechnology Information Gene Expression Omnibus (NCBI GEO) with the accession number GSE44076. The platform of this dataset was GPL13667, which is the Affymetrix Human Genome U219 Array. The data included mRNA expression profiles from three types of tissues: tumor tissues of patients, normal tissues of patients (adjacent to the tumor), and normal tissues of healthy people. However, we only used data from the tumor and normal samples of patients. This selection was made to enable a focused investigation of the molecular and transcriptomic differences between tumor tissues and their matched adjacent normal tissues in colorectal cancer patients.

All the tumor and normal tissues were collected from patients who were newly diagnosed with colorectal adenocarcinoma and were confirmed histologically. All the tumor and adjacent normal tissues were obtained from patients diagnosed with stage II microsatellite-stable colorectal adenocarcinoma. Stage II patients were selected to reduce clinical and molecular heterogeneity, as this group represents an intermediate disease state with neither distant metastasis (as in stage III/IV) nor an extremely early stage. Focusing on stage II allowed for a clearer assessment of gene expression alterations associated with local tumor progression without the confounding effects of advanced disease or prior treatment. However, this selection may limit the generalizability of the findings to other disease stages, particularly those involving metastatic or treatment-resistant tumors. Further validation across multiple clinical stages is necessary to assess the broader applicability of the identified biomarkers and drug candidates. These patients were followed up for more than three years, did not receive neoadjuvant chemotherapy, and had microsatellite stable colon cancer.

- Methods

Dataset Preparation and Preprocessing: First, we cleaned the original dataset. This involved removing non-gene transcripts, like text descriptions, patient information, and other lines that did not include gene data. After this, the remaining gene data was analyzed using the “Limma” package from the Bioconductor project in RStudio (version 1.1.423). The Bonferroni method was used to adjust p-values and make the results more reliable.

Each gene was identified by its reference ID. Duplicated genes or those without a reference ID were removed. To choose the most important genes, we used two filters: the adjusted p-value had to be less than 0.01, and the absolute log-fold change had to be equal to or greater than 0.5. After filtering, we had 6208 differentially expressed genes (DEGs). These were then used to build the co-expression network and for further steps in the study.

Feature Selection of Genes: Next, to find the most important genes, we used Python to combine the dataset with platform GPL13667. This gave us a dataset with 98 tumor samples and 98 normal

samples. Instead of using the GEO2R tool, we employed the Univariate Feature Selection module from the Scikit-learn package in Python (version 1.3.2) using the SelectKBest function with the ANOVA F-statistic (`f_classif`) as the scoring metric. This allowed for objective ranking of features based on statistical significance. Genes were filtered based on a p-value threshold of < 0.01 , and only the top-ranked genes (selected based on visual inspection of the score distribution curve) were retained for downstream comparison with WGCNA results. This approach was selected for its reproducibility, integration capability with machine learning workflows, and flexibility in parameter tuning. This approach was chosen because it offers greater flexibility and control over statistical parameters, enabling the application of consistent and customizable feature selection criteria across high-dimensional datasets. Additionally, the use of Scikit-learn allows integration with downstream machine learning workflows and facilitates reproducibility through script-based analysis, which is more robust and scalable compared to the web-based GEO2R platform. This method helped us identify the most significant genes. These selected genes were later compared with the results obtained from the co-expression network analysis.

Building the Gene Co-expression Network: The 6208 DEGs were used to build a co-expression network. This network was created using the WGCNA package in RStudio (version 1.1.423). Before building the network, we used hierarchical clustering to find outliers in the normal and tumor samples. These outliers were removed from the analysis.

After removing the outliers, the remaining samples were used to construct the co-expression network. To construct the gene co-expression network, the WGCNA package in R was used with 6,208 filtered DEGs. Sample clustering was performed using average linkage hierarchical clustering with Euclidean distance to detect outliers, and samples with standardized connectivity Z-score < -2 were removed ($n = 4$). A soft-thresholding power (β) of 6 was selected based on the criterion of scale-free topology fit index ($R^2 > 0.9$) and acceptable mean connectivity. Module detection was carried out using the dynamic tree cut method with the following parameters: minimum module size = 30, `deepSplit = 2`, and `mergeCutHeight = 0.25`. Module preservation between tumor and normal groups was evaluated using the `modulePreservation` function in WGCNA, and `Zsummary` values were used to assess preservation strength. Only modules with `Zsummary` between 2 and 10 were considered moderately preserved and selected for downstream analysis.

Extracting Modules: Next, the adjacency matrix was created from the gene expression data. From this matrix, we created the topological overlap matrix, which helped in grouping similar genes. The hierarchical clustering method was used to detect modules, and different values for deep split and minimum module size were tested.

Each module was labeled with a different color. To combine similar modules, we calculated the dissimilarity of eigengenes and merged those with a similarity below the 0.3 threshold. Then we calculated `Zsummary` values to check how well each module was preserved. Modules with a `Zsummary` above 10 were considered strongly preserved but not useful for this study. Modules with `Zsummary` between 2 and 10 were moderately preserved and were selected for further analysis. There were no modules with a `Zsummary` below 2. In total, three modules were selected for the next steps.

mRNA-miRNA Bipartite Network: After selecting the modules, we looked for target miRNAs of the genes in those modules using the miRWalk database. Then, using Cytoscape (version 3.7.0), we constructed three bipartite networks that connected the selected genes to their regulating miRNAs. This step was based on data collected in October and November 2021.

For each module, we selected the ten miRNAs with the highest degree, meaning they were

connected to many genes. These were considered hub miRNAs because they likely play important roles in gene regulation. These hub miRNAs were used to build the final mRNA-miRNA networks. Gene Set Enrichment Analysis: We used the DAVID database to perform gene set enrichment analysis on the selected module genes. This analysis included biological processes, molecular functions, and cellular components, with results considered significant at $p < 0.01$. We also used the Reactome database to find important pathways involving the genes. Again, only those with $p < 0.01$ were reported. This data was also gathered in October and November 2021.

Enrichment of Genes and miRNAs in Subnetworks: We studied the functional categories of the selected hub miRNAs using the TAM tool. The tool gave results for miRNA families and functions, again with a p-value cutoff of 0.01. Also, we repeated the gene enrichment analysis on the genes targeted by these miRNAs using the DAVID database to understand their biological roles.

Drug-Gene Network Construction: Finally, we tried to find potential drugs that could regulate the selected genes. For this purpose, we used the DGIdb database and limited the results to approved drugs only. Using Cytoscape, we built two drug-gene networks. The analysis focused on drugs with high connectivity to genes, as they may have stronger or broader effects. This data was also collected in October and November 2021.

Results

Differentially Expressed Genes: The gene expression data used in this study came from the GSE44076 dataset. It had 98 colon cancer (CC) samples and 98 normal samples. The analysis found 6,208 genes that were significantly different between tumor and normal tissues. These genes were identified using adjusted p-values lower than 0.01 and log-fold changes greater than or equal to 0.5. These results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of microarray dataset

Dataset	Type of samples	Normal	Tumor	Expression array
GSE44076	mRNA	98 (Male:71, Female:27)	98 (Male:71, Female:27)	Affymetrix Human Genome U219 Arrays
		Mean \pm SD = 70/54 \pm 9/021		

Feature Selection: To find the most important genes, Python was used instead of the GEO2R tool. A dataset was created with 98 cancer and 98 normal samples. Then, univariate feature selection from the scikit-learn package was used. The most significant genes identified were ADH1B, AQP8, CA1, CLCA4, GUCA2B, MMP7, MS4A12, and TMIGD1. All of these genes were also found in the co-expression network analysis (WGCNA), showing that they are important in colon cancer.

Module Analysis: After building a co-expression network with 6,208 genes, the soft threshold value (β) was chosen using scale independence (R^2) and mean connectivity. A value of 6 was selected because it gave a high R^2 of 0.907. This step is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scale-free topology model fit (R^2) and mean connectivity used to select the soft-thresholding power (β). A soft-thresholding power of 6 was selected based on achieving a scale-free topology fit index ($R^2 > 0.9$), ensuring the co-expression network approximates a biologically relevant structure. This balance between network sparsity and connectivity was critical for robust module detection.

Next, a topological overlap matrix (TOM) was calculated to help find gene modules using hierarchical clustering. Modules were separated with different colors, and then some similar ones were merged. Outlier samples were identified and removed using hierarchical clustering based on sample connectivity measures within the WGCNA framework. Specifically, samples with standardized connectivity Z-scores below -2 were considered outliers. A total of four samples were excluded from the analysis based on this criterion. To evaluate module preservation between tumor and normal tissues, the Zsummary statistic was calculated for each module. Modules with Zsummary values between 2 and 10 were classified as moderately preserved and selected for further investigation. Three such modules were retained: green-yellow (Zsummary = 6.0, 203 genes), midnight blue (Zsummary = 7.0, 145 genes), and light cyan (Zsummary = 7.2, 453 genes). These modules represent co-expressed gene clusters with significant transcriptional alterations between cancerous and adjacent normal tissues and were used in downstream miRNA and drug repurposing analyses. These results are shown in Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 2. Zsummary statistics showing module preservation between tumor and normal tissues. Modules with Zsummary > 10 were strongly preserved and excluded from further analysis. Three moderately preserved modules (Zsummary 2–10) were retained for downstream functional and regulatory analysis.

Table 2. Description of the selected gene modules including Zsummary scores and number of genes.

	Module color	Value of Z _{summary}	Number of genes in the module
1	Green yellow	6.0	203
2	Midnight blue	7.0	145
3	Light cyan	7.2	453

These modules were prioritized due to moderate preservation and significant transcriptional variation between cancer and normal tissues, indicating potential roles in tumor biology

Gene-miRNA Bipartite Network and Hub miRNAs: Each selected module was used to build a bipartite network of genes and miRNAs. Ten miRNAs with the most connections (high degree) were selected for each module because they are likely more important in regulation.

- In the green-yellow module, there were 38 genes.
- In the light cyan module, there were 63 genes.
- In the midnight blue module, there were 24 genes.

Figures showing these three bipartite networks are Figure 3, Figure 4, and Figure 5.

Figure 5. Bipartite network of midnight blue module

The most significant genes from feature selection were found in the midnight blue module.

Enrichment Analysis of Modules' Genes: Gene Ontology (G.O.) and Reactome pathway analysis were used to find biological processes and pathways related to the modules.

- In the green-yellow module, functional enrichment analysis revealed several significantly associated pathways, including TGFB signaling, NFkB activation, Interleukin-10 signaling, and response to SARS-CoV-2, as well as biological processes such as protein deubiquitination, acute inflammation, and defense response to virus. These pathways were identified using the Reactome and DAVID databases with a significance threshold of $p < 0.01$. Among them, TGFB and NFkB signaling are particularly relevant to colon cancer pathogenesis, as they are well-documented regulators of tumor growth, immune evasion, and epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition. Interleukin-10 signaling also plays a dual role in modulating inflammation and tumor progression in the colonic microenvironment. Therefore, the green-yellow module likely captures immune-related transcriptional dysregulation critical to the initiation and progression of colon cancer.
- Light cyan module: Cell Cycle Checkpoints was the only significant pathway. Main biological processes include Notch and Wnt signaling, DNA replication, cell proliferation, and signal transduction.
- Midnight blue module: Important pathways include Chromosome Maintenance, G1/S and G2/M transitions, rRNA processing, and metabolism. Biological processes include drug response, telomere maintenance, and ventricular system development.

Enrichment Analysis of Genes and miRNAs in Bipartite Subnetworks: The TAM tool was used to analyze miRNAs in each subnetwork:

- Green-yellow: Families included miR-25, miR-193, miR-10, miR-122, and miR-124. Important functions were angiogenesis, apoptosis, cell proliferation, immune response, inflammation, and stem cell regulation.
- Light cyan: Families included miR-30 and let-7. Functions were tumor suppression, T-cell differentiation, and anti-cell proliferation.
- Midnight blue: Families included miR-3689 and miR-1233. Functions were DNA synthesis, bone regeneration, and epithelial-mesenchymal transition.

Then, the genes targeted by the top 10 miRNAs were enriched again using DAVID:

Discussion

This study combined co-expression network analysis and machine learning–based feature selection to identify candidate biomarkers and therapeutic agents for colon cancer. Unlike prior studies that focused solely on differential expression or pathway enrichment [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], this integrative approach cross-validated key genes such as MMP7, TMIGD1, and MS4A12—each of which has known or emerging relevance in colorectal tumorigenesis [26], [27]. For example, MMP7 is frequently linked with poor prognosis due to its role in extracellular matrix degradation and metastasis, while TMIGD1 and MS4A12 have been reported to possess tumor-suppressive activity. These findings not only confirm previously reported targets but also uncover novel candidates for functional validation [23], [24]. A total of 6208 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were found between the tumor and normal samples [25]. Then, co-expression networks were built using the WGCNA method. Feature selection methods also helped to find the most significant genes. These methods were used in combination to enhance the robustness of the findings, as WGCNA captures gene co-expression patterns and identifies biologically relevant gene modules, while feature selection statistically isolates the most differentially expressed genes. The overlap between results from both approaches served as a form of cross-validation, increasing confidence in the biological relevance of the identified genes [28], [29].

The co-expression network found different gene modules [30]. Three modules—green-yellow, midnight blue, and light cyan—were selected from the co-expression network based on their Zsummary values. These moderately preserved modules contained genes that exhibited substantial differential expression between tumor and normal tissues [31], [32]. The selected genes were then used to construct mRNA-miRNA bipartite networks. For each module, a group of ten miRNAs with the highest degree (the most connections) were chosen as hub miRNAs [8], [33]. These hub miRNAs were important because they may play a key role in regulating cancer-related genes [4], [5], [34].

In the green-yellow module, 38 genes and 10 hub miRNAs were included. In the light cyan module, 63 genes and 10 hub miRNAs were selected. In the midnight blue module, 24 genes and 10 hub miRNAs were found. Most of the most significant genes found by the feature selection method were in the midnight blue module [10], [35].

Functional enrichment analysis was done for genes and miRNAs. Using the DAVID and TAM tools, important biological functions and pathways were discovered. In the green-yellow module, the pathways included TGFB signaling, NFkB activation, and Interleukin-10 signaling. The biological processes included inflammation, immune response, and protein modification [36].

In the light cyan module, cell cycle checkpoints were important. Biological processes like signal transduction, apoptosis, protein phosphorylation, and DNA replication were found [37], [38]. The midnight blue module was involved in chromosome maintenance and cell cycle processes, such as G1/S and G2/M transitions. Other processes included drug response and telomere maintenance [11], [39].

The miRNAs in the networks belonged to well-characterized families such as let-7, miR-30, miR-130, and miR-193. These families have established roles in the regulation of oncogenic pathways in colon cancer and other solid tumors. For example, the let-7 family is widely recognized for its tumor-suppressive functions through inhibition of RAS and MYC oncogenes, while miR-30 is involved in modulating epithelial–mesenchymal transition and apoptosis. miR-130 has been associated with angiogenesis and chemoresistance, and miR-193 contributes to cell cycle regulation and inhibition of tumor cell proliferation. Their presence in the identified subnetworks

supports the biological relevance of the constructed mRNA–miRNA regulatory framework. These miRNAs were linked to functions like cell death, angiogenesis, tumor suppression, and immune response [40], [41]. The green-yellow subnetwork showed many biological functions related to immune response and apoptosis. The light cyan subnetwork included tumor suppression and T-cell differentiation [42]. The midnight blue subnetwork was related to DNA synthesis and cell differentiation.

The genes targeted by the ten hub miRNAs were also analyzed for enrichment. The biological processes from these genes matched the findings from the original modules. These included processes like protein phosphorylation, cell polarity, protein stability, and cellular responses to starvation or catabolic processes [4], [43].

After identifying the genes and miRNAs, the next step was to find potential drugs. The DGIdb database was used to identify FDA-approved drugs targeting genes within the selected WGCNA modules. Several agents—such as Fluorouracil, Methotrexate, and Doxorubicin—are already established in colorectal cancer therapy, which supports the reliability of our approach. Others, like Disulfiram and Simvastatin, have shown anti-cancer activity in preclinical colon cancer models [42], [43], [44], suggesting promising repurposing opportunities. This aligns with recent studies demonstrating the efficacy of non-traditional agents through mechanisms such as oxidative stress induction, immune modulation, and inhibition of metabolic pathways [44], [45], [46].

From the feature selection method, the most significant genes were ADH1B, AQP8, CA1, CLCA4, GUCA2B, MMP7, MS4A12, and TMIGD1. These genes appeared in the WGCNA-selected modules too, which shows consistency between the two methods. Many of these genes are related to cell growth, metabolism, and the immune system. Some genes like MMP7 are already known to be linked with poor colon cancer outcomes. Others like TMIGD1 and MS4A12 may have a tumor-suppressive role [26], [27].

Overall, this study employed an integrative computational approach that combined gene expression profiling, miRNA-mRNA network construction, and drug repurposing analysis to identify potential biomarkers and therapeutic candidates for colon cancer. Unlike traditional wet-lab methods, which are often time-consuming and resource-intensive, this *in silico* framework enables rapid, large-scale screening of molecular interactions and drug targets, making it especially effective for early-stage biomarker discovery. The study identified several candidate miRNAs and repurposed drugs with potential relevance to colon cancer pathogenesis and treatment. However, these findings remain theoretical and require further validation. Future work should include *in vitro* experiments (e.g., luciferase reporter assays, qRT-PCR, cell viability assays) to confirm gene and miRNA expression, as well as *in vivo* studies using animal models to assess therapeutic efficacy and safety in a biological context.

Applications and Limitations

The integrative computational approach employed in this study demonstrates the promising potential of bioinformatics tools in identifying novel biomarkers and repurposed drugs for colon cancer. The combination of WGCNA, feature selection, and mRNA–miRNA network analysis enabled the identification of key regulatory molecules and candidate therapeutic agents with high relevance to tumorigenesis and disease progression. Notably, several hub miRNAs and target genes identified in this study are involved in essential pathways such as inflammation, cell cycle control, and apoptosis, underscoring their therapeutic significance. Furthermore, the drug-gene interaction analysis revealed several approved drugs—such as Fluorouracil, Cytarabine, and Tretinoin—that could be repositioned for colon cancer treatment, potentially accelerating drug

development and reducing costs.

However, the study also presents limitations. All findings are based on *in silico* analyses and theoretical predictions, which require experimental validation. The absence of functional assays, *in vivo* models, and clinical data limits the direct applicability of these results in therapeutic settings. Additionally, the heterogeneity of colon cancer and variability in patient response to therapy were not addressed in this computational framework.

In conclusion, this study highlights the utility of systems biology and bioinformatics in accelerating biomarker discovery and drug repurposing for colon cancer. Future work should focus on validating these findings through laboratory experiments, clinical trials, and multi-omics integration to ensure robust translation from code to cure.

Conclusion

This study aimed to discover new genes, miRNAs, and drugs that may be important for colon cancer (CC). Using gene expression data, co-expression networks, and feature selection, eight key genes were found: ADH1B, AQP8, CA1, CLCA4, GUCA2B, MMP7, MS4A12, and TMIGD1. Three gene modules were selected using WGCNA, and for each one, a bipartite mRNA-miRNA network was built. From these, hub miRNAs such as hsa-miR-665, hsa-miR-30c-3p, hsa-let-7b-5p, hsa-miR-3689d, hsa-miR-1233-5p, hsa-miR-1910-3p, and hsa-miR-6788-5p were found. These miRNAs may act as biomarkers for colon cancer.

Finally, drug-gene interaction analysis suggested several repurposed drugs, including Cytarabine, Levodopa, Methyl dopa, Tretinoin, Hydralazine, Daunorubicin Hydrochloride, Olanzapine, and Idarubicin. These drugs were identified as potential candidates based on gene-drug interaction analysis, but their efficacy in colon cancer remains to be experimentally confirmed. However, more clinical and lab studies are needed to test their role and confirm their safety and effectiveness.

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Conflict of interests

There is no conflict of interest.

Reference

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